

THE MULTI-LINGUAL DATABASE SYSTEM*

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ABSTRACT

This paper introduces a new and unconventional approach to the design and implementation of a database system, the *multi-lingual database system (MLDS)*. The multi-lingual database system is a single database system that can execute many transactions written respectively in different data languages and support many databases structured correspondingly in various data models, i.e., DL/I transactions on hierarchical databases, CODASYL-DML transactions on network databases, SQL transactions on relational databases and Daplex transactions on functional databases. Thus, a multi-lingual database system allows the old transactions and existing databases to be migrated to the new environment, the experienced user to continue to utilize certain favorite features of existing data languages and data models, the new user to explore the strong features of the various data languages and data models, the hardware upgrade to be focused on a single system instead of a heterogeneous collection of database systems, and the database application to cover wider types of transactions and different modes of interactions.

1. INTRODUCTION

Data models, data languages and database systems have evolved over a number of years. For instance, in the sixties, IBM introduced the Information Management System (IMS), which supports the hierarchical data model and the hierarchical-model-based data language, Data Language I (DL/I). In the seventies, Sperry Univac introduced the DMS-1100 database system, offering the network data model and the network-model-based data language, CODASYL Data Manipulation Language (DML). The evolution continued with IBM's introduction of the SQL/Data System in the eighties which supports the relational model and the relational-model-based data language, Structured English Query Language (SQL) and with CCA's introduction of the Daplex data language based on the functional data model. As in the evolution of software-laden database systems, the hardware-assisted database systems followed the same pattern. Thus, the experimental CASSM³⁰ database machine of the seventies supported the hierarchical data model and data language. The prototyped XDMS⁷ database backend also of the seventies supported the network data model and CODASYL-DML. More recently, the Britton-Lee IDM/500 and the Teradata DBC/1012 support the relational data model and relational-model-based data languages similar to SQL.

Whether they are database software systems or database hardware machines, the conventional approach to their design and implementation has been typified by the following steps. First, a specific data model for the database system or machine is chosen. Second, a corresponding model-based data language is then specified. Finally, a system or machine which specifically supports the model and language is designed and implemented. The result of this traditional approach to the database-system development is a mono-lingual database system where the user sees and uses the database system with a specific data model and its model-based data language. The accepted practice for the database-system design and

implementation mandates that a database system must be mono-lingual, i.e., restricted to a single data model and a specific model-based data language. Why should a database system be restricted to a single data model and a specific model-based data language? In other words, why shouldn't a database system be multi-lingual? Let us review the evolution of operating systems before answering this question.

The early operating systems, like the present database systems, have individually supported a specific set of data structures and a single programming language which defines and manipulates the structured data. For example, the Fortran Monitor System of the fifties has supported an operating-system environment for a single programming language (i.e., Fortran) and its corresponding data structures (e.g., Fortran arrays and variables). As operating system evolved through the sixties and seventies and into the eighties, the same operating environment supported a variety of data structures and their programming languages. For example, the Unix operating system supports traditional programming languages such as C, Pascal, and Fortran, list-processing programming languages such as Lisp, and logic programming languages such as Prolog. All programs written in the aforementioned languages (using the corresponding data structures can be run in the same operating system which is also responsible for managing all of the physical resources shared by the running programs and their data structures.

Given this characterization of the operating-systems evolution, we can draw an interesting analogy between operating systems and database systems. The concepts of the modern operating systems, programming languages, data structures, and shared resources are analogous to the concepts of modern database systems, data languages, data models and shared databases. Since a modern operating system executes and supports the user's programs in different programming languages and data structures, a modern database system should also execute and support the user's transactions in different data languages and data models. Since a modern operating system provides access to and management of a common set of resources for the running programs, a modern database system should also provide access to and management of a large collection of shared databases for the running transactions. Finally, since a modern operating system provides many modes of access such as interactive programming and batch processing, a modern database system should also provide many modes of access such as ad-hoc queries and transaction processing. With this analogy, we respond to the question in the previous section that a modern database system should be able to support multiple data models and their different data languages and provide various modes of access to the databases. Such a modern database system is termed the *multi-lingual database system (MLDS)*.

The multi-lingual database system (MLDS), is a single database system that can execute many transactions written respectively in different data languages and support many databases structured correspondingly in various data models. For example, the multi-lingual database system can run DL/I transactions on hierarchical databases, CODASYL-DML transactions on network databases, SQL transactions on relational databases and Daplex transactions on functional databases, where the system appears to the user like a heterogeneous collection of database systems. Thus, the multi-lingual database system allows the old transactions and existing databases to

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be migrated to the new environment, the experienced user to continue to utilize certain favorite features of existing data languages and data models, the new user to explore the strong features of the various data languages and data models, the hardware upgrade to be focused on a single system instead of a heterogeneous collection of database systems, and the database application to cover wider types of transactions and different modes of interactions.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. In Section 2 we describe the multi-lingual database system, focusing on its practical merits, new functionalities, theoretical issues, and basic structure. We also examine other approaches to supporting multiple data models and languages, as well as the implementation details of MLDS. In Section 3, we examine the mapping techniques, in particular, mapping relational and hierarchical data to the data of MLDS, as well as mapping SQL and DL/I operations to the operations of MLDS. Finally, in Section 4 we conclude this paper, indicate our other related work, and speculate on our future work in MLDS.

2. THE MULTI-LINGUAL DATABASE SYSTEM

2.1. Issues and Merits of MLDS

The issues and merits of the multi-lingual database system fall into three categories. First, by studying the *practical merits* of MLDS, we are able to demonstrate the concrete and useful features of such a system. Second, by identifying the *new functionalities* inherent in MLDS, we are able to provide the incentives for the user to move from a conventional database system to MLDS. Third, by verifying the *theoretical issues* required to support multiple data models and data languages in MLDS, we may gain a better understanding into the structures of and relationships among different data models and data languages.

One practical advantage of the multi-lingual database system involves the reusability of database transactions developed on existing database systems. Since MLDS provides an environment for running database transactions written in different data languages, the transactions written in a specific data language on another database system can also be executed in MLDS. There is no need to translate a transaction written in one data language to another data language in order to run the transaction in the other database system, even if the database has been converted from the original form to the present one. For example, had we wanted to run a transaction (written in DL/I and run on IMS) in SQL/DS, we would have to translate the DL/I transaction to the equivalent SQL transaction, since SQL/DS is a relational system and does not run DL/I transactions. However, in a multi-lingual database system, both SQL and DL/I are supported, so there is no need of any translation from DL/I to SQL. Nor is there a need of translation from SQL to DL/I. MLDS can execute transactions written in either DL/I or SQL. Thus, MLDS provides an environment in which "old" transactions never die and "new" transactions can continue to be written in the same (old) data languages.

The second practical advantage of a multi-lingual database system lies in the economy and effectiveness of hardware upgrade. As for any database system there comes a time when a hardware upgrade is required due to technology advancement or system demand. The upgrade of MLDS will benefit all of the user transactions whether the transactions are written, for instance, in SQL, DL/I, CODASYL-DML, or Daplex. In the conventional environment where there are separate database systems for separate data languages, all of the database systems would need to be upgraded. For our example, the conventional upgrade involves the hardware of SQL/DS, of IMS, of DMS-1100 and of Daplex system, resulting in greater expense and more effort.

One new functionality of a multi-lingual database system is to allow the new users to explore the strong points of different data models and to utilize desirable features of different data languages for their applications. This is because MLDS can be used to support

databases structured in any of the well-known data models such as relational, hierarchical, network, or functional and to execute transactions written in any of the well-known data languages such as SQL, DL/I, CODASYL-DML, or Daplex.

The other new functionality of MLDS is the availability of its native data model and data language. The native data model of MLDS is called the *kernel data model (KDM)*, and the native data language the *kernel data language (KDL)*. The term "kernel" is meant to be "central" or "core" or "essential". The difference between a conventional data model and the kernel data model is that all of the databases structured in a conventional data model can be transformed into equivalent databases structured in the kernel model. Further, all of the conventional data languages can be translated into the kernel data language. It is important to note that KDM (KDL) as a data model (language) is at a high level like other data models (languages) such as the relational data model (SQL data language), the hierarchical data model (DL/I data language), the network data model (CODASYL-DML data language) and the functional data model (Daplex data language). Thus, there is no reason why the users should not also explore the strong points of KDM and the desirable features of KDL for their applications.

In searching for a kernel data model and kernel data language with a high-level structure, which will support different data models and data languages, we are examining the transformations of various data models into the kernel data model and the translations of various data languages to the kernel data language. The mapping process from a given data model to KDM is called *data-model transformation*. The mapping process from a given data language to KDL is called *data-language translation*. To design a multi-lingual database system, the data-model transformations and data-language translations must be specified. By specifying the various data-model transformations, e. g., from the relational model to the KDM, from the hierarchical model to KDM, from the network model to the KDM, and from the functional model to the KDM, we may also examine the transformation process to determine the commonalities and differences of the different transformations. Similarly, by providing various data-language translations, e. g., from SQL to KDL, from DL/I to KDL, from CODASYL-DML to KDL and from Daplex to KDL, we may also study the translation process to identify the common and different translation techniques. Finally, once all of the data-model transformations and data-language translations have been specified, we can examine the complexity of the transformation and translation processes.

2.2. The Organization of MLDS

The system structure of a multi-lingual database system is shown in Figure 1. Users issue transactions through the language interface layer (LIL) using a user-chosen data model (UDM) and written in a corresponding model-based data language (UDL). LIL then routes the user transactions to the kernel mapping system

Figure 1. The Multi-Lingual Database System (MLDS).

(KMS). KMS has two tasks. First, if the user specifies that a new database is to be created, KMS transforms the UDM-database definition to an equivalent kernel-data-model-(KDM)-database definition. The KDM-database definition is then sent to the kernel controller (KC). KC sends the KDM-database definition to the kernel database system (KDS). Upon completion, KDS notifies KC, which in turn, notifies the user that the database definition has been processed and that the loading of the database may commence.

The second task of KMS is to handle UDL transactions. In this situation, KMS translates the UDL transaction to an equivalent kernel-data-language (KDL) transaction. KMS then sends the KDL transaction to KC, which in turn, sends the KDL transaction to KDS for execution. Upon completion, KDS sends the results in KDM form back to KC. KC forwards these results to the kernel formatting system (KFS) for transforming them from the KDM form to the UDM form. After the data is transformed, KFS returns the results, i.e., the response set, to the user via LIL.

There is one final note of importance on the general system structure. Four of the five components of the multi-lingual database system, namely, LIL, KMS, KC, and KFS, are referred to as a *language interface*. A new language interface is required for each chosen data language. For example, there is a set of LIL, KMS, KC, and KFS for the relational/SQL language interface, a separate set of these four components for the hierarchical/DL/I language interface, a third set of components for the network/CODASYL-DML language interface and a fourth set for the functional/Daplex language interface. KDS, on the other hand, is a single and major component that is accessed and shared by all of the various language interfaces as depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Multiple Language Interfaces for the Same Kernel Database System.

2.3. Other Approaches to MLDS

In the areas of data-model transformation and data-language translation, there are other efforts. In one effort, the goal is to examine the capability of an existing database system in supporting another data model and language on the existing system. The work of Katz¹⁸ supports the network data model and CODASYL-DML data language on a relational system. Furthermore, the support of the relational data model and data language on a network system and the support of the network data model and data language on a relational database system have been examined by Larson.²² Each of these examinations is essentially restricted to the mapping from one data model and data language to another data model and data language. We refer to their approaches as the *one-to-one mapping approach*.

The other effort in data-model transformation and data-language translation focuses on communicating with a heterogeneous collection of separate database systems via a local-area network. In this effort, a global data model and global data language is defined.

By using a global data model and global data language, the user is able to obtain uniform access to a number of database systems based on different data models and data languages.¹⁴ The CCA Multibase System,²⁸ UCLA DBMS,⁸ SDC Mermaid³¹ and NBS XDMS²⁰ are examples of database systems each of which maps a single(global) data model and single(global) data language to a collection of data models and data languages, e.g., the *one-to-many mapping approach*.

It is interesting to note that MLDS described herein maps respectively many different data models and data languages to a single(kernel) data model and a single(kernel) data language which is the *many-to-one mapping approach*. The one-to-many mapping approach is the reverse of the many-to-one mapping approach and the one-to-one mapping approach is a special case of the more general case of the many-to-one mapping approach.

2.4. The Implementation of MLDS

The four language interfaces of MLDS (i.e., the SQL, DL/I, CODASYL-DML and Daplex language interfaces) are implemented on a VAX-11/780 running the 4.2 B.S.D Unix operating system. All of the modules of each language interface have been coded using the C programming language.¹⁹ The size of each language interface ranges from 4,000 to 5,000 lines of code. Initially, the interaction between the language interface and the kernel database system (KDS) is simulated. After each language interface is thoroughly debugged and tested, it is then integrated with KDS. The integrated version of four language interfaces is currently operational at the Laboratory for Database Systems Research.

2.4.1. Choosing a Kernel Data Model and Language

As a prerequisite for examining our experience with MLDS, we first explore the two goals of the mapping process, i.e., data-model transformation and data-language translation. In data-model transformation, we must be sure that the data semantics are preserved. When converting a database (modeled in, for example, one of the four aforementioned models) to a kernel database, we must insure that an equivalent and complete database can be created. In other words, the source(user) database and the transformed target(kernel) database have the same semantics. In data-language translation, we must be sure that the translated transaction operations are equivalent. Thus, when translating a source(user) transaction (written in, for example, one of the four aforementioned data languages) to a target(kernel) transaction written in the kernel data language, we must insure that the access of the stored database as required by the source transaction. Consequently, semantic preservation of the database and operational equivalence of the transactions are respectively the goals of the data-model transformation and the data-language translation.

To us, the key decision in the development of a multi-lingual database system is therefore the choice of a kernel data model and kernel-model-based data language, so that semantic preservation and operational equivalence can be facilitated with ease. In our effort, we experiment with the attribute-based data model proposed by Hsiao¹⁶, extended by Wong³⁴, and studied by Rothnie²⁹ as the kernel data model. The attribute-based data language (ABDL) defined in Banerjee² and extended by Tung³² is therefore chosen as the kernel data language. The main question is whether or not the attribute-based data model and data language are capable of supporting the required data-model transformations and data-language translations. Is it easy to transform a relational, hierarchical, network or functional database to an attribute-based database with the data semantics intact? Can SQL, DL/I, CODASYL-DML and Daplex operations be translated easily to ABDL operations with the transaction operations being equivalent?

The series of papers^{3,4,5} have shown how the relational, hierarchical, and network data can be transformed to attribute-based data and also presented some preliminary work on the corresponding data-language translations. More recently, the complete sets of

algorithms for the data-language translation from SQL to ABDL^{25,27}, from DL/I to ABDL,³³ from CODASYL-DML to ABDL,³⁵ and from Daplex to ABDL,¹⁶ have been specified. Software development efforts for the language interfaces, (i.e., one set of LIL, KMS, KFS, and KC for the relational interface⁶, another set for the hierarchical interface²¹ and a third set for the network interface¹³), and a fourth set for the functional interface^{1,24} have been completed.

Another, equally important reason, for choosing the attribute-based data model as the kernel data model and ABDL as the kernel data language lies in the availability of a research database system in the Laboratory for Database Systems Research. This database system, the *multi-backend database system (MBDS)*, uses respectively the attribute-based data model and ABDL as the native data model and data language of the system. Thus, MBDS can serve as an ideal test bed for KDS. The interested reader may refer to Demurjian and Hsiao^{11,12} for an overview of the structure and operation of MBDS.

2.4.1.1. The Attribute-Based Data Model

In the attribute-based data model, data is considered in the following constructs: database, file, record, attribute-value pair, keyword, attribute-value range, directory keyword, non-directory keyword, directory, record body, keyword predicate, and query. Informally, a *database* consists of a collection of files. Each *file* contains a group of records which are characterized by a unique set of keywords. A *record* is composed of two parts. The first part is a collection of *attribute-value pairs* or *keywords*. An attribute-value pair is a member of the Cartesian product of the attribute name and the value domain of the attribute. As an example, <POPULATION, 25000> is an attribute-value pair having 25000 as the value for the population attribute. A record contains at most one attribute-value pair for each attribute defined in the database. Certain attribute-value pairs of a record (or a file) are called the *directory keywords* of the record (file), because either the attribute-value pairs or their attribute-value ranges are kept in a *directory* for identifying the records (files). Those attribute-value pairs which are not kept in the directory are called *non-directory keywords*. The rest of the record is textual information, which is referred to as the *record body*. An example of a record is shown below.

```
(<FILE, USCensus>, <CITY, Monterey>,
 <POPULATION, 25000>, {Temperate climate})
```

The angle brackets, <,>, enclose an attribute-value pair, i.e., keyword. The curly brackets, {}, include the record body. The first attribute-value pair of all records of a file, by convention, is the same. In particular, the attribute is FILE and the value is the file name. A record is enclosed in the parenthesis. For example, the above sample record is from the USCensus file.

The records of the database may be identified by keyword predicates. A *keyword predicate* is a 3-tuple consisting of a directory attribute, a relational operator (=, !=, >, <, ≥, ≤), and an attribute value, e.g., POPULATION ≥ 20000 is a keyword predicate. More specifically, it is a greater-than-or-equal-to predicate. Combining keyword predicates in disjunctive normal form characterizes a *query* of the database. The query

```
(FILE = USCensus and CITY = Monterey) or
(FILE = USCensus and CITY = San Jose)
```

will be satisfied by all records of the USCensus file with the CITY of either Monterey or San Jose. For clarity, we also employ parentheses for bracketing conjunctions in a query.

2.4.1.2. The Attribute-Based Data Language (ABDL)

The attribute-based data language supports the five primary database operations, INSERT, DELETE, UPDATE, RETRIEVE, and RETRIEVE-COMMON. A *request* in the ABDL is a primary operation with a qualification. A *qualification* is used to specify the part of the database that is to be operated on. Two or more requests may be grouped together to form a *transaction*. Now, let us illustrate the five types of requests and forgo their formal specifications.

The INSERT request is used to insert a new record into the database. The qualification of an INSERT request is a list of keywords with or without a record body being inserted. In the following example, an INSERT request that will insert a record

```
INSERT (<FILE, USCensus>, <CITY, Cumberland>,
 <POPULATION, 40000>)
```

without a record body into the USCensus file for the city Cumberland with a population of 40,000.

A DELETE request is used to remove one or more records from the database. The qualification of a DELETE request is a query. The following example is a request that will delete all records whose

```
DELETE ((FILE = USCensus) and (POPULATION > 100000))
```

population is greater than 100,000 in the USCensus file.

An UPDATE request is used to modify records of the database. The qualification of an UPDATE request consists of two parts, the query and the modifier. The *query* specifies which records of the database are to be modified. The *modifier* specifies how the records being modified are to be updated. The following example is an

```
UPDATE (FILE = USCensus)
(POPULATION = POPULATION + 5000)
```

UPDATE request that will modify all records of the USCensus file by increasing all populations by 5,000. In this example, (FILE = USCensus) is the query and (POPULATION = POPULATION + 5000) is the modifier.

The RETRIEVE request is used to retrieve records of the database. The qualification of a retrieve request consists of a query, a target-list, and a by-clause. The query specifies which records are to be retrieved. The target-list consists of a list of output attributes. It may also consist of an aggregate operation, i. e., AVG, COUNT, SUM, MIN, MAX, on one or more output attribute values. The optional by-clause may be used to group records when an aggregate operation is specified. The RETRIEVE request in the following example will retrieve the city names and populations of all records

```
RETRIEVE ((FILE = USCensus) and
(POPULATION ≥ 50000)) (CITY, POPULATION)
```

in the USCensus file whose populations are greater than or equal to 50,000. ((FILE = USCensus) and (POPULATION ≥ 50,000)) is the query and (POPULATION, CITY) is the target-list. There is no use of the by-clause or aggregation in this example.

Lastly, the RETRIEVE-COMMON request is used to merge two files by common attribute-values. Logically, the RETRIEVE-COMMON request can be considered as a transaction of two retrieve requests that are processed serially. In the following example, the

```
RETRIEVE ((FILE = CanadaCensus) and
(POPULATION ≥ 100000)) (CITY)
COMMON (POPULATION, POPULATION)
RETRIEVE ((FILE = USCensus) and
(POPULATION ≥ 100000)) (CITY)
```

RETRIEVE-COMMON request will find all records in the CanadaCensus file with population greater than 100,000, find all records in the USCensus file with population greater than 100,000, identify records of respective files whose population figures are common, and return the two city names whose cities have the same population figures. ABDL provides five seemingly simple database operations, which are nevertheless capable of supporting complex and comprehensive transactions.

2.4.2. Implementing the Kernel Mapping System

The heart of the kernel mapping system (KMS) is a parser-translator. As mentioned earlier, our development environment is the Unix operating system. To program the KMS parser-translator we utilized two compiler-generation tools provided by Unix, namely, Lex²³ and YACC.¹⁷ Lex, short for lexical analyzer generator, is a program generator designed for lexical processing of input character

streams. Given a regular-expression description of the input strings, LEX generates a program that partitions the input stream into tokens and provides these tokens on demand to the parser. Yacc, short for yet-another-compiler compiler, is a program generator designed for the syntactic processing of a tokenized input stream. In our case, the input strings to Lex are transactions written in UDL, i. e., transactions written in SQL, DL/I, CODASYL-DML, or Daplex. The tokenized version of these transactions is passed to Yacc. Yacc takes the tokenized transaction and verifies it against a set of grammar rules which describe the UDL grammar, i. e., a Backus-Naur form (BNF) representation of SQL, DL/I, CODASYL-DML, or Daplex. As Yacc parses the tokenized transaction, the mapping of the UDL transactions to KDL transactions occurs, i.e., the mapping of SQL to ABDL, DL/I to ABDL, CODASYL-DML to ABDL, or Daplex to ABDL. At the completion of this phase, Yacc generates a list of one or more KDL transactions that are equivalent to the input UDL transaction. This list of KDL transactions is then passed to the kernel controller (KC) for execution. One final note, the size of the KMS module of each language interface consists of approximately 1,500 to 2,500 lines of C and Yacc code, thereby comprising about half of the total software size of a language interface.

3. TRANSFORMATIONS AND TRANSLATIONS

In this section we provide examples for two particular data-model transformations, i.e., from relational to attribute-based and from hierarchical to attribute-based. In this presentation, we stress how we obtain the semantic preservation of UDM in KDM. This section also provides an overview of the two corresponding data-language translations, i.e., from SQL to ABDL and from DL/I to ABDL. In this presentation, we provide some insight into how KC insures the semantic preservation of UDM in KDM, achieves operational equivalence of UDL in KDL, and mimics the UDM-UDL execution environment. Due to obvious space limitations, we do not include herein our other work on data-model transformations (i.e., from network to attribute-based and from functional to attribute-based). Nor do we include herein our other work on data-language translation (i.e., from CODASYL-DML to ABDL and from Daplex to ABDL). Even on the data-language translations of the relational to attribute-based and hierarchical to attribute-based, we resort to a partial presentation to conserve space. The reader is referred to Demurjian¹⁰ for a complete and formal presentation of data-model transformation and data-language translation techniques.

3.1. The Data-Model Transformations

3.1.1. Relational Data to Attribute-Based Data

Relational data is organized into *tuples of relations*. A *database* is a collection of relations. The attributes of a relation are distinct. The tuples of a relation have the property that no two tuples are identical. A definition of the Course-Prereq-Offering relational database which we use in subsequent examples is given in Figure 3.

```
Course(Course#, Title, Descrip)
Prereq(Course#, Pcourse#)
Offering(Date, Location, Format)
Schedule(Course#, Date)
```

Figure 3. A Relational Version of the Course-Prereq-Offering Database.

Briefly, let us describe the data relationships of this database. First, each course is uniquely identified by a course number, and has a title and a description, i. e., the Course relation. A particular course may have one or more prerequisite courses, i. e., the Prereq relation. An offering describes the where (date), when (location) and how (format) of courses offered in the database, i.e., the Offering relation. A particular course may have one or more offerings, uniquely identified by the date of the offering, i.e., the Schedule relation.

The mapping of the relational data to the attribute-based data is straightforward. The concepts of a database, a relation, and a

tuple in the relational data correspond to a database, a file, and a record in the attribute-based data. So, the relational database shown in Figure 3 can be mapped to the attribute-based database given in Figure 4.

```
(<File, Course>, <Course#, value>, <Title, value>,
  <Descrip, value>)
(<File, Prereq>, <Course#, value>, <Pcourse#, value>)
(<File, Offering>, <Date, value>, <Location, value>,
  <Format, value>)
(<File, Schedule>, <Course#, value>, <Date, value>)
```

Figure 4. An Attribute-Based Representation of the Relational Course-Prereq-Offering Database.

In Figure 4, each relational attribute has been transformed into an attribute-based keyword. Unlike the relational specification in Figure 3, where the values of the tuples need not appear, the attribute-based specification in Figure 4 requires a place holder in each keyword for the attribute value. This place holder is denoted with the word "value." Additionally, a keyword which identifies the relation has been added, i.e., the one with the attribute File.

3.1.2. Hierarchical Data to Attribute-Based Data

Hierarchical data is organized into *occurrences of segments*. A *database* is a collection of segments, structured in a hierarchical or tree-like fashion. The occurrences in a given segment have the property that no two occurrences are identical. The fields of an occurrence are distinct. Additionally, an occurrence in one segment may correspond to one or more occurrences of another segment. Such a correspondence is often characterized as a parent-child relationship between the two segment types, i.e., a parent has one or more children. A definition of the Course-Prereq-Offering hierarchical database, equivalent to the relational database of Figure 3, is given in Figure 5.

* Denotes the Sequence Field of the Segment

Figure 5. A Hierarchical Version of the Course-Prereq-Offering Database.

In the hierarchical version of the database, courses are uniquely identified by course numbers and have titles and descriptions, i.e., the Course(root) segment occurrences. Each course has one or more prerequisite courses (i.e., a one-to-many relationship), as indicated by the arrow between the Course and Prereq segments in Figure 5. Similarly, each course has one or more dates on which the course is offered (i.e., also a one-to-many relationship), as indicated by the arrow from the Course segment to the Offering Segment. A hierarchy has levels. The (root) level of the root segment is defined to be level 0. The children of the root are at level 1. The grandchildren of the root are at level 2, and so on.

The mapping of the hierarchical data to the attribute-based data is also straightforward. The concepts of a database, a segment, and an occurrence in the hierarchical data correspond to a database, a file, and a record in the attribute-based data. The major emphasis when mapping hierarchical data to attribute-based data is to somehow encode the one-to-many relationships represented in the hierarchy. This of course must be done in order to insure that the data semantics of the hierarchical data are preserved in the attribute-based data. To capture the hierarchical relationship of any segment in the hierarchy, we include in the attribute-based record the sequence fields along the hierarchical path from the root segment to a particular segment. In this way, the hierarchical database shown in

Figure 5 can be mapped to the attribute-based database given in Figure 6. Again, we use "value" as the place holder for a particular attribute value.

```
(<File, Course>, <Course#, value>, <Title, value>,
  <Descrip, value>)
(<File, Prereq>, <Course#, value>, <Pcourse#, value>,
  <Title, value>)
(<File, Offering>, <Course#, value>, <Date, value>,
  <Location, value>, <Format, value>)
```

Figure 6. An Attribute-Based Representation of the Hierarchical Course-Prereq-Offering Database.

In Figure 6, we see that each field of a segment occurrence has been transformed into a keyword of a record. In order to differentiate between segments, the segment name has been included as an attribute value in the File keyword. This of course corresponds to the method used to encode the relation name in Figure 4. Finally, we see that the sequence field for the Course segment has been cascaded into the attribute-based record types for Prereq and Offering. This is used to capture the one-to-many relationship between the Course segment and the Prereq segment, and between the Course segment and the Offering segment. The method in which the kernel controller utilizes and maintains the one-to-many relationships of a hierarchical database within the attribute-based equivalent is discussed in Section 3.2.2.

3.2. The Data-Language Translations

3.2.1. SQL Queries to ABDL Requests

In this section, we present an informal overview of the translation of SQL SELECTS and SQL nested-SELECTS, to ABDL RETRIEVE requests. We also explore the execution sequence that the kernel controller (KC) oversees to insure the operational preservation of the SQL queries as their translated ABDL requests are being sent to KDS (i.e., MBDS) for execution. For detailed techniques for translating this and the remaining SQL query types, the reader is to refer to the work of Macy,²⁵ Rollins,²⁷ and Klopping and Mack.²¹

Consider the general form of an SQL SELECT query as shown below. In our notation, square brackets ([]) denote an optional portion of a language statement. The select-list is a list of one or more attribute names, with aggregate operators optionally applied. The from-list is a list of one or more table names. The boolean-expr has

```
SELECT      select-list
FROM        from-list
[WHERE      boolean-expr]
[GROUP BY  attribute-name]
[ORDER BY  attribute-name]
```

two possibilities. First, it is a regular boolean expression involving attribute names, relational operators, attribute values and boolean operators. Second, a boolean-expr may refer back to a SELECT query. In the second case, we have a nested-SELECT query. The GROUP BY and ORDER BY are optional operations that are used for sorting the result data.

Let us now consider two different data-language translation examples against the relational database given in Figure 3. Our first example, is a simple SQL SELECT query to find and then sort the prerequisite courses for the CS4322 course.

```
SELECT      Course#,Pcourse#
FROM        Prereq
WHERE       Course# = CS4322
ORDER BY    Pcourse#
```

We recall that the general form for an ABDL RETRIEVE request is
RETRIEVE query target-list [BY attribute-name].

The query of the ABDL request must be specified in disjunctive normal form. The target-list consists of the attributes to be retrieved from the database with optional aggregate operators applied. The optional BY clause is used to sort the data.

To translate the simple SQL SELECT, we first generate the query of the ABDL RETRIEVE. The query consists of the combination of the boolean expression in the WHERE clause (i.e., Course# = CS4322) with a predicate to identify the attribute-based file being referenced (i.e., File = Prereq). These two keywords can be easily combined into a disjunctive normal form to yield the query ((File = Prereq) and (Course# = CS4322)). The next component of the ABDL RETRIEVE is the target-list, which simply consists of the attributes in the select-list of the SQL SELECT, namely, (course#, Pcourse#). The final component of the ABDL RETRIEVE is the BY clause, and is a direct translation from the SQL ORDER BY clause, yielding, BY Pcourse#. By concatenating these three components together, the simple SQL SELECT is translated into the ABDL RETRIEVE shown below. For submission to the KDS (i.e., MBDS), the request is enclosed in curly braces.

```
{RETRIEVE ((File = Prereq) and (Course# = CS4322))
  (Course#, Pcourse#) BY Pcourse#}
```

After the translation is complete, the ABDL request is passed to KC. KC controls the execution process of the request in order to insure operational equivalence. For the straightforward translation just described, KC submits the ABDL request to KDS. When the results are returned from KDS, they are routed to KFS for subsequent display. In this case, KFS displays the results in tabular form.

Our second example, shown below, is a SQL nested-SELECT query. This nested-SELECT finds the course numbers and dates of

```
SELECT      Course#,Date
FROM        Schedule
WHERE       Date IN
            (SELECT      Date
             FROM        Offering
             WHERE       Location = Monterey)
```

all courses offered in Monterey. The data-language translation process for a SQL nested-SELECT is accomplished in a similar fashion to the previous example. However, in this case, a list of two ABDL RETRIEVE requests, R1 and R2, one for each of the SELECTS, are generated:

```
R1  {RETRIEVE ((File = Offering) and
  (Location = Monterey)) (Date)}
R2  {RETRIEVE ((File = Schedule) and
  (Date = *****)) (Course#, Date)}
```

Notice that the first request, R1, corresponds to the inner nested-SELECT (i.e., the one involving the Offering relation). On the other hand, R2 corresponds to the outer nested-SELECT (i.e., the one involving the Schedule relation). In the general case, a n-level nested-SELECT query translates to n ABDL RETRIEVE requests. We also notice that R2 is specified with a place holder (denoted by the asterisks). The specification of the query of R2 depends upon the attribute values of Date. To execute R2, we must first execute R1, to determine the Dates involved. Unlike the first example, KC must play an important role in sequencing the execution of R1 and R2.

The goal of KC is to insure operational equivalence. To achieve this goal, KC must execute R1 and R2 in a sequential, non-overlapped fashion. KC begins by sending R1 to KDS for processing. After the first request is executed by KDS, instead of forwarding the results to the KFS, the results are buffered within the KC module. KC uses the buffered results to execute the second request. Suppose that the request R1 returns the results

Date
860115
860230
860301

Taking these results from the buffer, KC would form R2 to yield the request

```
{RETRIEVE (((File = Schedule) and (Date = 860115)) or
((File = Schedule) and (Date = 860230)) or
((File = Schedule) and (Date = 860301))) (Course#, Date)}
```

Note that we must take care to produce an ABDL query that is in disjunctive normal form. KC then sends this newly formed request to KDS for execution, collects the results and forwards them to KFS as usual. Thus, KC plays a vital role in insuring the operational equivalence of the SQL nested-SELECT.

3.2.2. DL/I Requests to ABDL Requests

We now present an overview of the data-language translation from DL/I GU and GN statements to ABDL RETRIEVE requests. Our major emphasis in this section is examining the execution sequence and responsibilities of KC to insure operational equivalence. The complete data-language translation from DL/I to ABDL is documented by Weishar.³⁵ The implementation of the DL/I language interface, is reported by Benson and Wentz.⁶

The general form of a DL/I GU or GN differs only in the operation type, and is shown below. The dml-operator can be either GU, GN or any of the other DL/I operations. To access a

```
dml-operator  seg-srch-arg
              [seg-srch-arg-list]
```

segment occurrence, we specify the segment in the segment-search argument (seg-srch-arg) which includes the segment name and an optional boolean expression. The segment-search-argument list (seg-srch-arg-list) is an optional list of one or more segment search arguments.

When a DL/I GU or GN is translated, one or more ABDL RETRIEVE requests may result. Thus, the translation of DL/I requests is similar to the translation of SQL nested-SELECTS. For example, consider the DL/I GU request shown below.

```
GU   Course (Title = Advanced Database Systems)
     Prereq
```

This DL/I GU retrieves all prerequisites for the advanced-database-systems course. It also retrieves the course number of the advanced-database-systems course. In translating this statement, two ABDL RETRIEVE requests, R3 and R4, are generated:

```
R3  {RETRIEVE ((File = Course) and (Title =
Advanced Database Systems)) (Course#) BY Course#}
R4  {RETRIEVE ((File = Prereq) and (Course# =
*****)) (Course#, Pcourse#, Title) By Pcourse#}
```

The sorting, via the BY clause, is used to simulate the hierarchical structure of the data in an IMS system. This in turn helps insure the operational equivalence of the ABDL requests. In the general case, a n-level DL/I GU or GN translates to n ABDL RETRIEVE requests.

The emphasis here is on the execution sequence of requests R3 and R4 by KC. KC begins by executing R3. When R3 is sent to KDS for execution, a course number corresponding to the advanced-database-systems course is returned in the result buffer. Say, the returned course number is CS4322. KC takes this course number and reforms the request R4 by inserting CS4322 for the place holder marked by asterisks. The reformed request R4 is then sent to KDS for processing. Suppose that the result of this request is

Course#	Pcourse#	Title
CS4322	CS3450	Systems Programming
CS4322	CS4300	Intro. Database Systems

In this case, KFS would forward the first result in this buffer, namely, "CS4322, CS3450, Systems Programming", to the user (i.e., recall that a GU is logically equivalent to a get-first and is used to establish

the current position of the database). At this point, the current position of the database has been established at the second segment occurrence in the result buffer.

Now suppose, that the DL/I statement GN Prereq appears at the LIL. This statement is also translated into R4 by KMS, and is then sent to KC. Due to the intelligence of KC, the request R4 is not resubmitted to KDS for processing. Instead, using the current position of the database, the second segment occurrence of the result buffer, namely, "CS4322, CS4300, Intro. Database Systems", is forwarded to the user. Besides operational equivalence, KC of the hierarchical language interface is also able to provide optimizations on data access and retrieval.

3.2.3. Comments on the Data-Language Translations

Our main goal in the development of the multi-lingual database system is to demonstrate the feasibility of supporting many languages within a single database system. To this end, we made certain decisions concerning the implementation of the four language interfaces. In both the relational and the hierarchical language interfaces, there are a number of features that have been omitted to simplify the implementation effort. In the relational/SQL interface, the facilities of views, security, updating multiple attributes in a single SQL UPDATE request, computing algebraic expressions in the select-list, eliminating duplicates, and retrieval using union have all been omitted. In the hierarchical/DL/I interface, the facilities of logical database records, segment insertion based on current position, and supporting some of the infrequently utilized segment-search-argument command codes have been omitted. The reader is referred to Kloepping and Mack²¹ and Benson and Wentz⁶ for a more detailed account of the omissions in the relational and hierarchical interfaces, respectively. However, we feel that these decisions in no way compromise our goal of demonstrating multi-language support.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

We do not provide a traditional conclusion to this paper. Instead, we provide some thoughts on our future work, which may be characterized by the three questions below.

Question One: Can we develop techniques that can be used to compare and contrast the different data-model transformations in order to provide a paradigm for measuring or gauging the complexity of data models? Our intention is to show that there may be a ranking of data models with respect to a data model's semantic richness. Our use of the techniques so far suggests that the data models can be ranked as follows, with respect to their semantic richness:

Semantic Richness	Data Model	Relationships Among Data Aggregates
Highest	Entity-Relationship	Self-Referencing and Generalization Relationships
High	Network	Many-to-Many Relationships
Medium	Hierarchical	One-to-Many Relationships
Low	Relational and Attribute-Based	Data-Grouping Relationships

As we proceed from the bottom to the top of the table, each data model inherits the relationships of the previous data models, i.e., the network data model has many-to-many, one-to-many, and data-grouping relationships among their data aggregates. Thus, semantic richness may be defined in terms of relationships.

Question Two: How can we estimate, gauge and measure the complexity of a data-language translation? Our study indicates that the complexity of a data-language translation is dependent on three different things: (1) the type of source and target data languages (i.e., procedural vs. non-procedural), (2) the degree of history sensitivity (i.e., data currency) that is required to carry out the source data-language operations and that is supported by the target data language, and (3) the data relationships that are supported by the

underlying data model of both the source and target data languages. That is, given particular instances of source and target data languages, we can examine the complexity of a data-language translation by identifying the three characteristics listed above for each data language. We can also develop a scheme by which we can compare and contrast the different data-language translations via the above characteristics. The reader is referred to Demurjian¹⁰, for a complete and detailed examination of the answers to the first two questions.

Currently, each database is accessed via either the language interface that created the database or via the kernel data language (i.e., ABDL) directly. This leads us to the third question.

Question Three: Can we provide access to a database by way of different language interfaces? For instance, can we allow the user of the Daplex language interface to access a database created by a CODASYL-DML language interface, i.e., to access a CODASYL-DML database with Daplex? The current version of MLDS restricts the use and access of databases. When a user of the relational/SQL language interface creates a database, that database is only accessible via SQL or ABDL. Similarly, hierarchical databases are only accessible via DL/I or ABDL, network databases are accessible via CODASYL-DML or ABDL and functional databases are accessible via Daplex or ABDL. We believe we have a system that would remove these restrictions. The implications of such a system are profound. By allowing the databases based on different data models to be accessed by data languages based on different data models, we extend our multi-lingual database system to a multi-model database system as well. The work of Rodeck²⁶ and Coker⁹ indicates that a truly multi-lingual-and-multi-model database system is in sight.

REFERENCES

- [1] Anthony, J. A. and Billings, A. J. "The Implementation of an Entity-Relationship Interface for the Multi-Lingual Database System" Master's Thesis, Naval Postgraduate School (NPS), Monterey, CA, Dec. 1985.
- [2] Banerjee, J. and Hsiao, D. K., "DBC Software Requirements for Supporting Relational Databases," The Ohio State University, Tech. Rep. No. OSU-CISRC-TR-77-7, Nov. 1977. See also [4,5].
- [3] Banerjee, J. and Hsiao, D. K., "A Methodology for Supporting Existing CODASYL Databases with New Database Machines," *Proceedings of National ACM Conference*, 1978.
- [4] Banerjee, J. and Hsiao, D. K., "The Use of a Database Machine for Supporting Relational Databases," *Proc. 5th Workshop on Computer Architecture for Nonnumeric Processing*, Aug. 1978.
- [5] Banerjee, J., Hsiao, D. K., and Ng, F., "Database Transformation, Query Translation and Performance Analysis of a Database Computer in Supporting Hierarchical Database Management," *IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering*, Vol. SE-6, No. 1, Jan. 1980.
- [6] Benson, T. P. and Wentz, G. L., "The Design and Implementation of a Hierarchical Interface for the Multi-Lingual Database System," Master's Thesis, NPS, Monterey, CA, June 1985.
- [7] Canaday, R. E., et al., "A Back-end Computer for Data Base Management," *Communications of the ACM*, Vol. 17, No. 10, Oct. 1974.
- [8] Cardenas, A., and Pirahesh, M. H., "Data Base Communication in a Heterogeneous Data Base Management System Network," *Information Systems*, Vol. 5, No. 1, 1980.
- [9] Coker, H., "On Accessing Functional Databases via CODASYL Transactions," Master's Thesis, NPS, Monterey, CA, Mar. 1987.
- [10] Demurjian, S. A., "The Multi-Lingual Database System - A Paradigm and Test-Bed for the Investigation of Data-Model Transformations, Data-Language Translations and Data-Model Semantics," Ph. D. Dissertation, The Ohio State University, Columbus, Ohio, Dec. 1986.
- [11] Demurjian, S. A. and Hsiao, D. K., "New Directions in Database-Systems Research and Development," *Proceedings of the International Symposium on New Directions in Computing*, Trondheim, Norway, Aug. 1985.
- [12] Demurjian, S. A., Hsiao, D. K., and Menon, J., "A Multi-Backend Database System for Performance Gains, Capacity Growth, and Hardware Upgrade," *Proceedings of the 1986 2nd International Conference on Data Engineering*, Los Angeles, CA, Feb. 1986.
- [13] Emdi, B., "The Implementation of a Network CODASYL-DML Interface for a Multi-Lingual Database System," Master's Thesis, NPS, Monterey, CA, Dec. 1985.
- [14] Gligor, V. D., and Luckenbaugh, G. L., "Interconnecting Heterogeneous Database Management Systems," *IEEE COMPUTER*, Vol. 17, No. 1, Jan. 1984.
- [15] Goisman, P. L., "The Design and Analysis of a Complete Entity-Relationship Interface for the Multi-Backend Database System" Master's Thesis, NPS, Monterey, CA, Dec. 1985.
- [16] Hsiao, D. K., and Harary, F., "A Formal System for Information Retrieval from Files," *Communications of the ACM*, Vol. 13, No. 2, Feb. 1970; *Corrigenda*, Vol 13., No. 4, Apr. 1970.
- [17] Johnson, S. C., "Yacc: Yet Another Compiler Compiler," Computer Science Technical Report No. 32, Bell Laboratories, Murray Hill, NJ, 1975.
- [18] Katz, R. H., and Wong, E., "Decompiling CODASYL DML into Relational Queries," *ACM Transactions on Database Systems*, Vol. 7, No. 1, Mar. 1982.
- [19] Kernighan, B. W., and Ritchie, D. M., *The C Programming Language*, Prentice-Hall, 1978.
- [20] Kimbleton, S. R., and Wang, P., "Application and Protocols," in *Distributed Systems: Architecture and Implementation*, Lecture Notes in Computer Science, Lampson and Siegart, eds., Vol. 105, Springer-Verlag, NY, 1981.
- [21] Klopping, G. R. and Mack, J. F., "The Design and Implementation of a Relational Interface for the Multi-Lingual Database System," Master's Thesis, NPS, Monterey, CA, June 1985.
- [22] Larson, J. A., "Bridging the Gap Between Network and Relational Database Management Systems," *IEEE COMPUTER*, Vol. 16, No. 9, Sept. 1983.
- [23] Lesk, M. E., "Lex - A Lexical Analyzer Generator," Computer Science Technical Report No. 39, Bell Laboratories, Murray Hill, NJ, 1975.
- [24] Lim, B., "The Design and Implementation of a Functional Interface for the Multi-Lingual Database System," Master's Thesis, NPS, Monterey, CA, Dec. 1986.
- [25] Macy, G., "Design and Analysis of an SQL Interface for a Multi-Backend Database System," Master's Thesis, NPS, Monterey, CA, Mar. 1984.
- [26] Rodeck, B. D., "Accessing and Updating Functional Databases Using CODASYL-DML," Master's Thesis, NPS, Monterey, CA, June 1986.
- [27] Rollins, R., "Design and Analysis of a Complete Relational Interface for a Multi-Backend Database System," Master's Thesis, NPS, Monterey, CA, June 1984.
- [28] Rosenberg, R. L., and Landers, T., "An Overview of MULTIBASE," *Distributed Data Bases*, H.-J. Schneider, ed., North-Holland Publishing Company, 1982.
- [29] Rothnie, J. B. Jr., "Attribute Based File Organization in a Paged Memory Environment," *Communications of the ACM*, Vol. 17, No. 2, Feb. 1974.
- [30] Su, S. Y. W., et al., "The Architectural Features and Implementation Techniques of the Multicell CASSM," *IEEE Transactions on Computers*, Vol. C-28, No. 6, June 1979.
- [31] Templeton, M., et al., "Mermaid - Experiences with Network Operation," *Proceedings of the 1986 2nd International Conference on Data Engineering*, Los Angeles, CA, Feb. 1986.
- [32] Tung, H. L., "Design, Analysis and Implementation of the Primary Operation, Retrieve-Common, of the Multi-Backend Database System (MBDS)," Master's Thesis, NPS, Monterey, CA, June 1985.
- [33] Weishar, D., "Design and Analysis of a Complete Hierarchical Interface for a Multi-Backend Database System," Master's Thesis, NPS, Monterey, CA, June 1984.
- [34] Wong, E., and Chiang, T. C., "Canonical Structure in Attribute Based File Organization," *Communications of the ACM*, Vol. 14, No. 9, Sept. 1971.
- [35] Worthly, C. R., "The Design and Analysis of a Network Interface for a Multi-Lingual Database System," Master's Thesis, NPS, Monterey, CA, Dec. 1985.